

The Putative Role of Methylglyoxal in Arterial Stiffening: A Review

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Background

Arterial stiffening is a hallmark of vascular ageing and a consequence of many diseases including diabetes mellitus. Methylglyoxal (MGO), a highly reactive α -dicarbonyl mainly formed during glycolysis, has emerged as a potential contributor to the development of arterial stiffness. MGO reacts with arginine and lysine residues in proteins to form stable advanced glycation endproducts (AGEs). AGEs may contribute to arterial stiffening by increased cross-linking of collagen within the extracellular matrix (ECM), by altering the vascular structure, and by triggering inflammatory and oxidative pathways. Although arterial stiffness is mainly determined by ECM and vascular smooth muscle cell function, the effects of MGO and MGO-derived AGEs on these structures have not been thoroughly reviewed to date.

Methods and Results

We conducted a PubMed search without filtering for publication date which resulted in 16 experimental and 22 clinical studies eligible for inclusion. Remarkably, none of the experimental and only three of the clinical studies specifically mentioned MGO-derived AGEs. Almost all studies reported an association between arterial stiffness and AGE accumulation in the arterial wall or increased plasma AGEs. Other studies report reduced arterial stiffness in experimental models upon administration of AGE-breakers.

Conclusions

No papers published to date directly show an association between MGO or MGO-derived AGEs and arterial stiffening. The relevance of the various underlying mechanisms is not yet clear, which is particularly due to methodological challenges in the detection of MGO and MGO-derived AGEs at the molecular, intra- and pericellular, and structural levels, as well as in challenges in the assessment of intrinsic arterial wall properties at ECM- and tissue levels.

Keywords

Advanced glycation endproduct • Dicarbonyls • Vascular stiffness • Pulse wave velocity • Distensibility • Cross-linking

Introduction

Large artery stiffening is an independent predictor of cardiovascular risk and cardiovascular mortality in the general population [1,2]. The process is associated with the development of end organ damage such as heart failure, chronic

kidney and cerebrovascular disease [3,4]. Arterial stiffening naturally occurs with age, and involves changes in extracellular matrix (ECM) components in the arterial wall [5]. Elastin and collagen are major components of the ECM. With ageing, the relatively elastic elastin fibres undergo proteolytic degradation and chemical alteration [6], leading to a

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shift in load towards the stiffer collagen fibres [7]. Moreover, ageing also involves increased production of collagen, in part by vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs) [8]. Chemical modifications of ECM components are thought to be an additional factor, causing the arterial wall to stiffen with age [9]. Arterial stiffening appears to be accelerated under pathological conditions, such as diabetes mellitus (DM) [10,11]. With the increasing incidence of DM [12], early detection of its vascular complications as well as understanding their development is a major challenge.

Over the past decade, the potential role of advanced glycation endproducts (AGEs) in arterial stiffening has emerged [13]. AGEs are formed by a non-enzymatic reaction of reduced sugar with proteins [14].

Among other risk factors, high blood glucose levels in diabetic patients might be one of the reasons these patients are typically more prone to AGE formation [11,15]. This effect may be exacerbated by consumption of a habitual diet with a high glycaemic load, which has been shown to be associated with higher concentrations of AGEs measured in the urine [16]. AGEs may contribute to arterial stiffening by (increased) cross-linking of collagen within the ECM, by altering the vascular structure [17], and by triggering inflammatory and oxidative pathways which contribute to endothelial dysfunction [18,19] and activation of VSMCs (Figure 1). It is now becoming clear that it is not glucose but rather α -dicarbonyls that are major precursors in the formation of AGEs. Among the group of α -dicarbonyls, methylglyoxal (MGO) is believed to be the most reactive precursor in the formation of AGEs [11].

There is considerable evidence that MGO engenders the development of vascular complications [20,21], underlining the importance of MGO in arterial stiffening. MGO is formed as a by-product of glycolysis, and is increased in patients with DM and hypertension [11]. MGO primarily reacts with arginine and lysine residues, forming stable AGEs. The most prevalent MGO-derived AGE *in vivo* is N δ -(5-hydro-5-methyl-4-imidazol-2-yl)ornithine (MG-H1) which results from the reaction of MGO with arginine. The reaction of MGO with lysine residues leads to formation of N ϵ -(1-carboxyethyl)lysine (CEL) as well as the lysine dimer 1,3-di(N ϵ -lysino)-4-methylimidazolium (MOLD) [11]. Additionally, MGO can cross-link lysine and arginine residues, resulting in 2-ammonio-6-((2-[4-ammonio-5-oxido-5-oxopentyl]amino)-4-methyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-5-ylidene)amino)hexanoate (MODIC) [22].

Under physiological conditions, MGO is detoxified into non-harmful D-lactate by the glyoxalase system [23]. Glyoxalase-1 (GLO-1; Figure 1) is the rate-limiting enzyme in the glyoxalase system. GLO-1 activity decreases with age in human vascular tissue [24]. Subsequently, the capacity to detoxify MGO by GLO-1 decreases and MGO accumulates. Increased MGO levels damage the arterial wall and may thereby contribute to vascular ageing in the elderly [24,25]. Furthermore, GLO-1 activity is downregulated by hyperglycaemia, hypoxia and inflammation [26]. Under these conditions the capacity of GLO-1 may be insufficient to

detoxify MGO (Figure 1), which further promotes vascular damage by MGO.

Although there is substantial evidence that MGO is directly linked to vascular complications, the role of MGO in arterial stiffening is less clear [27]. Current studies report complex and variable effects of MGO on arterial stiffness, but the focus of these studies is mostly on advanced glycation endproduct-receptor for advanced glycation endproducts (AGE-RAGE) interaction and endothelial dysfunction associated with increased arterial stiffness (Figure 1). The effects of MGO on ECM properties that largely determine arterial stiffness, and on VSMC function and phenotype have not been thoroughly reviewed to date. Therefore, the present narrative review focusses on the pleiotropic effects of MGO and MGO-derived AGEs on large artery stiffening with a particular focus on ECM remodelling.

Methods

We conducted a PubMed search without filtering for publication date. We included multiple search terms for arterial stiffness, and MGO and MGO-derived AGEs to identify content in published title and/or abstract (Syntax 1).

First, we excluded 1) reviews, 2) non-English full text publications, and 3) publications focussing on a non-systemic arterial domain. Second, we read title and full abstract to 1) exclude any leftover noneligible paper based on the above-mentioned exclusion criteria and 2) excluded all papers missing specific arterial stiffness measures and/or AGE measures.

Results

The primary search was performed on 1 December 2020, and resulted in 92 papers. Initial selection led to the exclusion of 25 papers (Figure 2). After reading title and full abstract, an additional 29 papers were excluded. Because the number of papers specifically investigating MGO and/or MGO-derived AGEs was very limited, and because AGE characterisation is methodologically challenging, we did not exclude papers investigating other (non-specified) AGEs at this stage. At completion of selection, 38 papers were retained for detailed analysis (Figure 2), which were separated into experimental (n=16) and clinical (n=22) studies.

Figure 1 illustrates the associative links between MGO and/or MGO-derived AGEs and arterial stiffening, as considered and discussed in the papers we reviewed.

Experimental Studies

None of the included experimental papers directly focussed on the specific role of MGO in arterial stiffening, but instead reported on AGEs. Most studies used a diabetes model to investigate the effect of AGEs on arterial stiffness (n=8; Table 1). Almost all studies (15 out of 16) were intervention studies, reporting the effect of AGE-breakers or AGE scavengers on arterial stiffness. None of the papers quantified

Figure 1 Pathways of methylglyoxal (MGO) and MGO-derived advanced glycation endproducts studied in reviewed papers with a particular focus on arterial stiffening. Bold text elements indicate the focus of the papers included in the present review. ① and ② indicate the two main pathways studied in the literature found, where ① entails focus on ECM remodelling and ② entails focus on RAGE interaction. Green elements in the figure reflect physiological MGO scavengers. Inhibition of MGO formation via GLO-1 is inhibited by inflammation and oxidative stress. sRAGE and esRAGE levels increase with increasing RAGE binding.

Abbreviations: RAGE, receptor for advanced glycation endproducts; sRAGE, soluble RAGE; esRAGE, endogenous secretory RAGE; GLO-1, glyoxalase-1; ECM, extracellular matrix; VSMC, vascular smooth muscle cell.

specific MGO-derived AGEs. Pulse wave velocity (PWV), the current gold standard to assess arterial stiffness in clinical practice, was reported in five papers [28–32]. Despite blood pressure being an important confounder for stiffness [33,34], none of these studies corrected measured PWV for blood pressure. Other *in vivo* studies using catheter-based haemodynamic measurements reported aortic input impedance or systemic arterial compliance as indirect markers of arterial stiffness ($n=10$; [35–44]). Two (2) of the latter studies additionally reported carotid distensibility coefficients [38,41]; one study reported stiffness index β [45].

We scrutinised all experimental studies for their thoroughness in assessing underlying structural changes at the ECM level (Table 1). Five (5) studies included *ex vivo* mechanical testing in addition to *in vivo* measurements [28,30,32,39,42]. These studies are highlighted in more detail below.

Huijberts *et al.* evaluated the effect of the AGE-breaker (also known as an AGE-inhibitor) aminoguanidine on various measures reflecting arterial wall stiffness in rats with streptozotocin (STZ) induced diabetes [39]. In addition to *in vivo* aortic impedance, the static mechanical properties of the arterial wall were assessed by measuring pressure-volume relationships in the *in situ* isolated carotid artery. Furthermore, *ex vivo* measurements were performed before and after intravascular incubation with potassium cyanide, to assess the influence of VSMC tone. Aminoguanidine-treated rats had an increased arterial compliance as compared to the untreated ones. Carotid artery compliance

remained clearly elevated in the treated group at a specified range (75–100 mmHg) during experiments without VSMC tone. Taken together, treatment with aminoguanidine significantly decreased artery wall stiffness. This could potentially be due to reduced AGE accumulation in the ECM, as targeted with aminoguanidine treatment.

In a following paper, the same experimental protocol as mentioned above was performed in STZ-induced diabetic rats treated with ALT-711 (also known as alagebrium), a different AGE-breaker [42]. The diabetes-induced increase in large artery stiffness, as assessed *in vivo* by aortic impedance and arterial compliance, and *ex vivo* by carotid artery distensibility and compliance, was reversed after ALT-711 treatment.

Although the reduction in arterial stiffness under the influence of ALT-711 and aminoguanidine have been confirmed in other studies [31,36,38,41,43–45] the mechanisms of action remain to be elucidated since the sub- and microstructural levels at which these compounds allegedly have an effect were not addressed in these studies (Figure 1). Because both ALT 711 and aminoguanidine are potentially effective in reducing MGO [9,11], the reduction of arterial stiffness by these compounds may be explained by a decrease of MGO.

Du *et al.* [32] studied the contribution of AGEs to stiffening in the murine aorta of low-density lipoprotein receptor deficiency ($LDLr^{-/-}$) mice, and the dependence of this stiffening on the presence of perivascular adipose tissue (PVAT). PVAT from $LDLr^{-/-}$ mice secreted larger amounts of the

Figure 2 Paper selection process.

*e.g., papers focussing on cerebral or ophthalmic effects of MGO only.

**any leftover papers that were categorised as review, were not available in English, or pertained to a non-systemic arterial domain.

Abbreviations: MGO, methylglyoxal; AGE, advanced glycation endproduct.

inflammatory cytokine interleukin-6 (IL-6). LDLr^{-/-} mice showed increased aortic stiffness, as quantified by *ex vivo* elastic modulus, compared to wild-type mice, but only when PVAT was present. An absence of PVAT reduced aortic stiffness in the LDLr^{-/-} to wild-type levels. Absence of PVAT also reduced adventitial AGE concentration, albeit not to wild-type levels. Therefore, the observed stiffening effect of PVAT may be attributable, at least partly, to a PVAT-derived IL-6 induced increase in AGEs.

PVAT-induced arterial stiffness was also observed in young compared to old C57BL/6 mice [30]. Administration of hesperidin and aminoguanidine ameliorated the age-dependent increase in aortic stiffness as well as the PVAT-mediated effects. Notably, both hesperidin and aminoguanidine have been shown to reduce MGO [11,46]. Although MGO or MGO-derived AGEs were not measured specifically in PVAT, these data may indicate that the accumulation of MGO in PVAT may contribute, at least partly, to age-related aortic stiffness.

Finally, Kohn *et al.* investigated the effect of exercise on subendothelial matrix stiffness in C57/BL6 mice [28]. An 8-week swimming regimen was followed by an 8-week sedentary rest period. PWV, subendothelial matrix stiffness (measured with atomic force microscopy), aortic intimal collagen levels and N^ε-(1-carboxymethyl) lysine (CML) accumulation were reduced after the exercise period, but returned to baseline after the sedentary rest period. Based on the concomitant decrease in aortic intimal collagen and CML, the authors propose that CML mainly influences arterial stiffness on the macro- and microscale, most probably via RAGE (Figure 1).

Taken together, in selected experimental studies, concomitant structural changes in the ECM and changes in vessel stiffness were associated with the presence or accumulation of AGEs. However, the included studies did not quantify MGO or MGO-derived AGEs in the vascular wall specifically.

Table 1 Overview of experimental studies.

Author	Year	Ref	Animal Model	Treatment	In Vivo Measurement	Tissue	AGE Measure	Main Finding
Chang	2006	[36]	Rat (Wistar), STZ DM	AG	Z_c , C_m , R_f , τ	Aorta	SDS-PAGE (anti-AGE AB 6D12)	8-wk AG treatment significantly reduced aortic characteristic impedance. Glycation-derived modification on aortic collagen was retarded by AG.
Chang	2009	[35]	Rat (Wistar), STZ DM	PM	Z_{iv} , C_m , R_f , τ	Aorta	SDS-PAGE	8-wk PM treatment significantly increased wave transit time and decreased wave reflection factor. Glycation-derived modification of aortic collagen was attenuated by PM administration.
Cheng	2005	[44]	Rat, STZ DM	C16, ALT-711	BP, HR, CO, TPR, SAC	Aorta	RBC-IgG -, tail tendon collagen solubility assay. IHC	C16 treatment significantly improved haemodynamic parameters and prevented an increase in collagen III/I ratio and AGE accumulation the aortic wall.
Cheng	2007	[43]	Rat, STZ DM	C36, ALT-711	BP, HR, CO, TPR, SAC	Aorta	RBC-IgG -, tail tendon collagen solubility assay. IHC	C36 treatment improved haemodynamics and improved tendon collagen solubility and normalized collagen type III/I ratio.
Chuang	2012	[37]	Rat (Wistar), CRF	Olmesartan	Z_{iv} , C_m , R_f , τ	Aorta	SDS-PAGE, IHC (anti-AGE AB 6D12)	Olmesartan ameliorated AS with concomitant inhibition of MDA and AGE levels through reduction of oxidative stress in the aortic wall.
Corman	1998	[38]	Rat (WAG/Rij)	AG	cDC, SAC	Aorta	-	Age related increase in aortic impedance and decrease in cDC were prevented by AG. AG did not affect aortic wall histological structure, suggesting that prevention of AS resulted from the effect of AG on cross-linking of ECM proteins.
LaRocca	2013	[29]	Mouse (C57BL/6)	Spermidine	aPWV	Aorta	-	Spermidine supplementation reversed age-associated increases in aortic pulse wave velocity and normalised levels of aortic collagen I and AGEs.
Liu	2003	[45]	Dog Alloxan induced DM	ALT-711	β	Left ventricle	Collagen solubility	ALT-711 reduced aortic stiffness and reversed upregulation of collagen type I and III. Additionally, collagen solubility increased, suggesting less cross-linking in the aortic wall.
Satheesan	2014	[40]	Rat, STZ DM	LR-90	Z_{iv} , C_m , R_f , τ	Aorta	IHC (anti-AGE antibody 6D12, anti-RAGE antibody)	LR-90 inhibited collagen cross-linking and the accumulation of AGE and RAGE in the vasculature of DM rats.
Shapiro	2008	[41]	Dog, Hypertension	ALT-711	Z_c , aDC	Left ventricle, Aorta	Collagen solubility, Western blot (α -CML AB), IHC (CML26 AB)	Aortic CML content was increased in hypertensive canine, independent of ALT-711 treatment, compared to younger ones. ALT-711 was associated with increased aortic distensibility and arterial compliance.
Vaitkevicius	2001	[31]	Rhesus monkey ^a	ALT-711	PWV, PWA			PWV and PWA decreased to a nadir at 6 wk post ALT-711 administration, and gradually increased to baseline values afterwards.

Table 1. (continued).

Studies with Ex Vivo Measures									
Author	Year	Ref	Animal Model	Treatment	In Vivo Measurement	Ex Vivo measurement	Tissue	AGE Measure	Main Finding
Du	2015	[32]	Mouse (C57BL/6), LDLr ^{-/-}	-	aPWV	<i>E</i>	Aorta	Western blot, IHC	LDLr ^{-/-} mice show increased aortic stiffness compared to wild-type mice. Mouse arteries cultured with PVAT had an increases collagen I and AGE content.
Huijberts	1993	[39]	Rat (Wistar), STZ DM	AG	<i>Z_c</i>	<i>C</i>	Common carotid artery	-	Treatment with AG significantly decreased artery wall stiffness. This could potentially be due to reduced AGE accumulation in the ECM.
Kohn	2018	[28]	Mouse (C57BL/6)	Exercise	PWV	<i>E</i>	Aorta	CML via ELISA	PWV of exercised mice significantly decreased but increased to a level of the sedentary counterparts after rest period. CML content decreased following exercise and returns to baseline after rest period.
Ouyang	2017	[30]	Mouse (C57BL/6)	Hesperidin, AG	aPWV	<i>E</i>	Aorta	Western blot, IHC	Hesperidin ameliorated age-related increase in aortic stiffness and PVAT-mediated effects on arterial stiffening. Hesperidin reversed PVAT AGE accumulation, where PVAT AGE were shown to promote aortic stiffness with ageing.
Wolffenbuttel	1998	[42]	Rat (Wistar), STZ DM	ALT-711	<i>Z_c</i> , <i>C</i>	<i>C</i> , cDC	Common carotid artery	RBC-IgG -, tail tendon collagen solubility assay	DM-induced increase in large artery stiffness was reversed after ALT-711 treatment.

Abbreviations: AGE, advanced glycation endproduct; STZ DM, streptozotocin induced diabetes mellitus; AG, aminoguanidine; *Z_c*, aortic characteristic impedance; *C_m*, compliance; *R_f*, reflection factor; τ , wave transit time; SDS-PAGE, sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis; AB, antibody; PM, pyridoxamine; BP, blood pressure; HR, heart rate; CO, cardiac output; TPR, total peripheral resistance; SAC, systemic arterial compliance; RBC-IgG, red blood cell immunoglobulin G; IHC, immunohistochemistry; CRF, chronic renal failure; cDC, carotid distensibility coefficient; AS, arterial stiffness; ECM, extra-cellular matrix; (a)PWV, (aortic) pulse wave velocity; *E*, Young's elastic modulus; *C*, area compliance; AFM, atomic force microscopy; CML, N ϵ -(carboxymethyl)lysine; ELISA, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; PVAT, perivascular adipose tissue; RAGE, receptor for advanced glycation endproducts; PWA, pulse wave analysis.

^aThis study included *in vivo* measurements only.

Table 2 Overview of clinical studies.

Author	Year	Ref	Context/Cohort	AGE Measure	AGE Quantification Method	AS Measures	Main Finding
Baumann	2009	[47]	FLEMENGHO study	Plasma CML/ Carotid plaque CML	ELISA/IHC	cfPWV, cCC, cDC	↑plasma CML is related to ↑ carotid diameter, but no change in elastic properties.
Couppé	2017	[68]	Apparently healthy elderly	SAF	AGE-reader	PWA	SAF is associated with arterial stiffness in endurance runners and healthy controls.
Dadoniene	2015	[48]	Systemic sclerosis	SAF	AGE-reader	cfPWV, crPWV, PWA	AGE accumulation was higher in systemic sclerosis patients and AGE product's score was associated with ↑crPWV.
Demirci	2019	[59]	Haemodialysis	Serum AGE	ELISA	PWV	ADF was negatively correlated with serum AGE, and PWV.
Di Pino	2017	[60]	Type 2 DM	CML, sRAGE	ELISA	PWV, PWA	↑intake of dietary AGEs is associated with ↑arterial stiffness.
Di Pino	2019	[49]	Apparently healthy	sRAGE, esRAGE, CML, S100A12	ELISA	cfPWV, PWA	PWV was associated with S100A12 plasma levels, while IMT was associated with esRAGE levels.
Heier	2015a	[66]	Type 1 DM	sRAGE, esRAGE/ CML, MG-H1	ELISA/DELIFIA	cYEM	No protective effect of esRAGE/sRAGE against atherosclerosis. MG-H1 levels were ↑ at baseline, but not after 5 yr follow-up.
Heier	2015b	[67]	Type 1 DM	MG-H1	DELIFIA	cYEM	Serum levels of MG-H1 are associated with low-grade inflammation, but not with arterial stiffness in type 1 DM.
Huang	2013	[50]	Apparently healthy	Plasma AGEs	ELISA	cfPWV, PWA	AGE accumulation is related to arterial stiffness in an age dependent manner.
Llaurdo	2014	[52]	Type 1 DM	SAF, serum CML	ELISA	cfPWV	SAF is associated with AS in type 1 DM, no association was found with CML levels.
Mac-Way	2014	[53]	Peritoneal- and haemodialysis	SAF, plasma pentosidine	AGE-reader, HPLC	cfPWV, PWA	Positive association between SAF, aortic stiffness and enhanced wave reflection.
McNulty	2007	[54]	Hypertension	Plasma CML/CEL	ELISA	cfPWV, PWA	Plasma AGE concentration is ↑ in hypertensive patients and related to PWV independent of age and blood pressure.
Semba	2009	[56]	Apparently healthy	Serum CML	ELISA	cfPWV	Elevated AGEs are associated with increased AS.
Semba	2015	[57]	Apparently healthy elderly	Serum CML	ELISA	cfPWV	Elevated serum CML was associated with AS.
Stróżecki	2013	[61]	Diabetic nephropathy, CKD	Serum AGEs	Plasma fluorescence spectra	cfPWV	AGE accumulation and AS are ↑ in CKD, but a causal role of AGE accumulation in AS was not confirmed.
Sveen	2015	[62]	Type 1 DM	Skin glucosepane	Liquid chromatography- MS	cfPWV, PWA	↑skin glucosepane was correlated with ↑PWV.
Ueno	2008	[64]	End stage renal disease	SAF	AGE-reader	baPWV	↑SAF was associated with increased baPWV.

Table 2. (continued).

Author	Year	Ref	Context/Cohort	AGE Measure	AGE Quantification Method	AS Measures	Main Finding
van Eupen	2016	[58]	De Maastricht Study	Plasma pentosidine/ CML, CEL/SAF	HPLC/UPLC-MS/ AGE-reader	cfPWV, cPP	SAF and pentosidine levels were associated with ↑aortic stiffening. The association form cfPWV was more pronounced in patients with type 2 DM.
Watfa	2012	[63]	Apparently healthy	SAF	AGE-reader	cfPWV	AGE levels were significantly associated with cfPWV in young, but not elderly individuals.
Yoshida	2005	[65]	Type 2 DM	Serum pentosidine	ELISA	hbPWV, baPWV	Serum pentosidine was positively associated with AS and carotid IMT in patient with type 2 DM.
Intervention Studies							
Author	Year	Ref	Context/Cohort	MGO/AGE measure	Treatment	AS measures	Main finding
Kass	2001	[51]	Vascular stiffening ^a	-	ALT-711	cfPWV, C _A	PWV decreased by 8% with ALT-711.
Oudegeest	2013	[55]	Apparently healthy elderly	-	Exercise/ Alagebrium	cfPWV	Arterial stiffness did not change. Alagebrium had no independent effect on vascular function.

Abbreviations: AGE, advanced glycation endproduct; AS, arterial stiffness; CML, N ϵ -(Carboxymethyl)lysine; ELISA, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; IHC, immunohistochemistry; cfPWV, carotid-to-femoral pulse wave velocity; cCC, carotid compliance coefficient; cDC, carotid distensibility coefficient; SAF, skin auto fluorescence; PWA, pulse wave analysis; crPWV, carotid-radial pulse wave velocity; ADF, adjusted dietary fibre; DM, diabetes mellitus; sRAGE, soluble receptor for advanced glycation endproducts; esRAGE, endogenous secretory receptor for AGE; MG-H1, methylglyoxal-derived cyclic hydroimidazolone-1; DELFIA, dissociation-enhanced lanthanide fluorescent immunoassay; cYEM, carotid Young's elastic modulus; CEL, N ϵ -(1-carboxyethyl)lysine; CKD, chronic kidney disease; MS, mass spectrometry; baPWV, brachial-ankle pulse wave velocity; HPLC, high performance liquid chromatography – mass spectrometry; UPLC-MS, ultra-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry; cPP, central pulse pressure; hbPWV, heart-to-brachial pulse wave velocity; IMT, intima-media thickness; C_A, arterial volume compliance.

^aVascular stiffening was classified based on pulse pressure, systolic blood pressure and large artery compliance.

Clinical Studies

Table 2 lists the 22 selected clinical studies reporting on MGO or MGO-derived AGEs and arterial stiffening. Most studies (17 out of 22) considered carotid-to-femoral PWV as an outcome for arterial stiffness [47–63]. Two (2) studies reported PWV over the brachial-ankle trajectory [64,65], and two studies focussed on carotid artery stiffness, as assessed by carotid Young's elastic modulus (cYEM) [66,67]. cYEM captures local wall material stiffness rather than the stiffness of a vessel, which additionally depends on the wall geometry. One (1) study reported augmentation index or derivatives obtained from pulse wave analysis [68].

MGO or MGO-derived AGEs were measured in 3 out of 22 studies. Other studies included did not report on MGO or MGO-derived AGEs, but on other (non-specified) AGEs and/or skin autofluorescence (SAF; 17 out of 22). Two (2) studies were intervention studies considering the effect of ALT-711 on vascular function, not including any measurement of AGE levels [51,55] (Table 2).

Only three clinical studies employed reliable arterial stiffness measures (cYEM or carotid-to-femoral PWV) and reported on MGO-derived AGEs specifically [58,66,67].

The relationship between MG-H1 and cYEM was investigated by Heier *et al.* [67]. Although the main purpose of their study was to investigate the relationship between MG-H1 and early signs of atherosclerosis in children and adolescents with type 1 DM, cYEM was addressed as separate outcome measure. MG-H1 was obtained from fasting serum blood samples and quantified via dissociation-enhanced lanthanide fluorescent immunoassay. This cross-sectional study reported an increase in MG-H1 fasting serum levels in type 1 DM patients compared to healthy controls. MG-H1 was associated with low-grade inflammation (assessed by C-reactive protein), but not with cYEM or wall thickness (i.e., carotid intima-media thickness, cIMT). A second study from the same group reported on soluble RAGE (sRAGE) and MG-H1 in relation to atherosclerosis in young subjects with type 1 DM, once again assessing cYEM [66]. Within this 5-year follow-up study, the same methods were used as in their previous study. Additionally, sRAGE and endogenous secretory RAGE (esRAGE) were measured using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). In this study, authors show a possible protective effect of high levels of sRAGE on inflammation (Figure 1), but not on arterial stiffening or wall thickening [66]. MG-H1 serum levels were significantly higher in subjects with type 1 DM at baseline, but it was not associated with arterial stiffening after the 5-year follow-up.

We have recently studied the association between SAF, and plasma pentosidine, CML and MGO-derived CEL, with arterial stiffness in a large cohort study (n=862) [58]. This cross-sectional study used ultra-performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) coupled with fluorescence or mass spectrometry (MS) for the quantification of AGEs and assessed arterial stiffness via PWV. The study reported that higher levels of SAF, plasma pentosidine and CML are associated with increased arterial stiffness. This effect was more pronounced in

participants with type 2 DM. Plasma MGO-derived CEL was not associated with increased stiffness [58]. Other studies confirmed an association between SAF and arterial stiffness [62–64,68], and between plasma pentosidine and arterial stiffness [65] in different populations.

Taken together, several clinical studies showed an association between AGEs and arterial stiffness, but so far, a causal link between the two is lacking. The assessment of AGE formation and the possible effect on ECM remodelling remains extremely challenging in clinical studies because both AGE formation and ECM remodelling cannot be quantified at the level of the arterial wall directly.

Discussion

The present narrative review addresses the relevance of MGO and MGO-derived AGEs as contributors to arterial stiffening. However, our review exposes several challenges that need to be faced before we can draw the conclusion that MGO is directly involved in arterial stiffening via ECM remodelling.

Measurement of MGO and MGO-derived AGEs *In Vivo* and *Ex Vivo*

The various studies included in this review use different methods for AGE quantification. AGE quantification is a point of concern and correct measurements of AGEs is a major topic of research. Initially, ELISA was used to quantify AGEs. However, the development of specific AGE antibodies has proven difficult and as a result most ELISA measurements lack reproducibility and specificity [69,70]. Some of the included studies have used Western Blot analysis to quantify AGEs, with similar limitations as for ELISA measurements. UPLC-MS is currently the state-of-the-art technique when it comes to quantifying AGEs [70,71]. Different α -dicarbonyls (including MGO) as well as the MGO-derived AGEs CEL and MG-H1 can be identified via UPLC-MS. However, UPLC-MS is very expensive and time-consuming. Furthermore, for the detection of AGEs, samples need to be hydrolysed with enzymatic digestion or with acid in order to get free (modified) amino acids [70]. For hydrolysis under acidic conditions, it should be considered that some AGE, including MG-H1, become unstable. Ultimately, AGE measurements under these harsh conditions are not yet applicable for all AGEs.

Effect of MGO on the Vascular Wall

Although the reviewed literature suggests that AGEs indeed influence arterial wall structure and function, the precise action of MGO and MGO-derived AGEs on arterial stiffening has not been mapped to date, mainly due to the methodological difficulties in AGE quantification.

In our current selection we did not find any papers directly demonstrating the effect of MGO on arterial stiffness, but

only papers that provide complementary evidence. MGO and MGO-derived AGE formation in hypertension were studied by Wang *et al.* [72]. MGO, AGE, and oxidative stress levels in spontaneous hypertensive rats were higher compared to controls. Staining for MGO-derived AGEs revealed that most of the accumulation was in the endothelial layer, suggesting that MGO contributes to development of hypertension via endothelial dysfunction and vascular reactivity (Figure 1). Treating spontaneously hypertensive rats with aminoguanidine improved endothelium-dependent relaxation and prevented morphological damage of vascular tissue measured by wall thickness and media-to-lumen ratio [73], once again supporting the role of MGO in vascular stiffness.

Clinical studies focussing on arterial stiffening and AGEs mainly used plasma measurements of AGEs [47,49,50,52-54,56-61,65-67]. Most of them consider inflammatory and oxidative stress pathways as a link between AGEs and stiffening (Figure 1). Reactive oxygen species (ROS) resulting from oxidative stress can trigger phenotypic switching of VSMCs from a contractile to a more synthetic type [8]. Whether MGO or AGEs have a direct effect on VSMC, without the interference of ROS, is not yet fully understood. Under the influence of ROS, VSMCs begin to proliferate, migrate and start to synthesise ECM components [8,74]. The latter can explain the increase in collagen content that is found in some of the experimental studies [32,38,43-45]. However, these studies do not consider exactly when and how collagen fibre cross-links are formed, which could include newly formed as well as present fibres.

Furthermore, although collagen is an essential part of the ECM, more experimental evidence on the interplay between MGO and elastin would give valuable (additional) information on ECM remodelling. To the best of our knowledge, this interplay has not been studied in detail to date [9,75].

Some studies that did consider the effect of AGE-breakers on collagen type-1 in detail were performed using rat tail tendons [76,77]. Fessel *et al.* quantified AGEs (MG-H1, CEL) via high performance liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry, and performed uniaxial tension tests, as well as small angle X-ray scattering to quantify nanoscale collagen density differences in individual fascicles from Sprague-Dawley rat tails [77]. After MGO incubation, they found reduced side-to-side sliding of collagen molecules within fibrils rather than stiffening of the fibrils themselves. This was confirmed in similar experiments showing that AGEs reduced tissue viscoelasticity by severely limiting fibre-fibre and fibril-fibril sliding [76]. Because both studies used supraphysiological levels of MGO (5-30 mM), their results may not directly translate to lower concentrations. However, another study using incubation of rat tail tendon fascicles with a more physiological 0.2 mM MGO concentration, did confirm MGO-derived cross-link structures in senescent collagen [78]. If the same reduction in fibre-fibre and fibril-fibril sliding is present in collagen of the vessel wall remains to be elucidated.

Quantification of Large Artery Stiffness

The translation of observed ECM remodelling by AGEs to increased arterial stiffness is not evident; not only because arterial stiffness results from a complex interplay between the different arterial wall components, but also because the exposure of these components to MGO and/or MGO-derived AGEs *in vivo* is probably less direct than in experimental settings.

MGO or MGO-derived AGEs may enter the body via food ingestion, though such exogenous forms likely do not immediately reach VSMC or ECM components [79]. Alternatively, MGO can be formed intracellularly in endothelial cells and VSMC during glycolysis [11]. Whereas most cells downregulate the expression of glucose transporters under hyperglycaemic conditions, endothelial cells retain expression of non-insulin-dependent glucose transporters. Consequently, intracellular glucose concentration rises concomitantly with extracellular glucose concentrations such as in DM [80]. In VSMCs, the expression of glucose transporter 1 is upregulated by extracellular hyperglycaemia as well as endothelial injury and this may also lead to increased levels of MGO [81,82]. Intracellularly formed MGO might be secreted into the direct surrounding tissue where it may reach the ECM components. This direct exposure might have different effects and might explain why accelerated arterial stiffness is mainly found in diabetes models.

Confounding Effect of Blood Pressure

Clinical measures of large artery stiffness are substantially pressure dependent [33,34]. It is important to correct (changes in) stiffness measures for blood pressure, because blood pressure differences (e.g., due to hypertension) or changes (e.g., by interventions with anti-hypertensive drugs) are mostly concomitant in practice [83]. In addition to statistical correction, which is feasible in large cohort studies, several approaches have been proposed for calculating pressure independent stiffness measures [83,84]. These pressure-corrected measures offer the potential to distinguish the acute dependence of arterial stiffness (i.e., on blood pressure at the time of measurement) and remodelling effects that blood pressure as well as AGEs may have on intrinsic arterial stiffness.

Recommendations for Future Research

In addition to the ongoing development of reliable methods to detect AGEs, well-controlled experimental studies are needed. Given that downregulation of GLO-1 in the human aorta appears to be related to ageing [25] and age-related diseases [24], and arterial stiffening, MGO/GLO-1 over-expression models could help to get more insight. Studies should incorporate complementary and comprehensive assessment of *in vivo* arterial stiffness assessment (i.e., distensibility or PWV, and blood pressure) and *ex vivo* histology and UPLC measurements. Studies considering the effect of MGO on ECM remodelling mostly report changes in

collagen content or strength. However, information on the content and organisation of elastin in the ECM will be of added value, given that cross-linking effects of MGO may not be limited to collagen only [9]. Finally, comprehensive characterisation of arterial wall mechanics via dynamic pressure myography will be important, to relate *ex vivo* tissue findings to *in vivo* arterial stiffness measures, such as PWV [83].

Conclusions

To our knowledge, no papers published to date show a direct association between MGO or MGO-derived AGEs and arterial stiffening. The relevance of the various underlying mechanisms is not yet clear, which is particularly due to methodological challenges in (1) the detection of MGO and MGO-derived AGEs at the molecular, intra- and pericellular, and structural levels, as well as (2) the assessment of intrinsic arterial wall properties at ECM- and tissue levels.

Declarations

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Appendices. Supplementary Data

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlc.2021.06.527>.

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